

Magnitude of Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media and Its Associated Factors among Children with Chronic Otitis Media Attending Ear, Nose and Throat Clinic at Tertiary Centers in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Background: Worldwide, chronic otitis media (COM) is a common upper airway infection, with a potential to result in hearing loss if poorly managed. It is disproportionately prevalent in developing regions, including Ethiopia. However, its prevalence estimates along with its risk factors are not adequately investigated in the study setting.

Objective: To assess the magnitude of chronic otitis media and its associated factors in children attending otorhinolaryngology clinics at tertiary centers in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

Methods: A facility-based, cross-sectional study will be conducted at three public hospitals of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Data will be collected using a pretested, structured interviewer-administered questionnaire. Proportional stratified random sampling technique will be employed to recruit children diagnosed with COM. Data will be edited cleaned via Epi-info and analyzed using SPSS version 26. Data will be summarized using descriptive statistics. Logistic regression will be performed to identify association between dependent and independent variables, computing odds ratio. A p-value <0.05 will be considered significant. Texts, tables and figures will be used to present the results.

Results: Out of 120 studied children, 78 (65%) were males, and children's age ranged from seven months to five years, with median (interquartile range) of 3 (2–4) years. Of all children, 34.2% (95% CI: 26–43) were diagnosed of CSOM. Lack of exclusive breastfeeding history [AOR=14.00(95%CI: 4.42,44.36)], lack of full vaccination to age [AOR=10.44 (95%CI: (2.91,37.48)], history of attending a daycare center [AOR=3.46 (95%CI: (1.12,10.63)], presence of comorbidity [AOR=3.85 (95%CI: (1.28,11.56)], and recurrent AOM [AOR= 6.74 (95%CI: 1.65,27.58)] were the factors independently associated with CSOM.

Conclusion: One in three of children with COM visiting otorhinolaryngology had suppuration, and it was associated with certain characteristics. There is a serious need for better ear care and screening programs for early detection and management of this disease.

Keywords: Chronic suppurative otitis media, Preschool children, Ethiopia

Acronyms/Abbreviations

AOM	Acute Otitis Media
AOR	Adjusted Odds Ratio
COR	Crude Odds Ratio
CSOM	Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media
ENT	Ear, Nose and Throat
EPI	Expanded Program on Immunization
ET	Eustachian Tube
GC	Gregorian Calendar
MD	Medical Doctor
MUAC	Mid Upper Arm Circumference
PI	Principal Investigator
SOM	Serous Otitis Media
TASH	Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital
TM	Tympanic Membrane
URTI	Upper Respiratory Tract Infection

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Chronic otitis media (COM) is a broad clinical entity that can be defined as an indolent pathology of the tympanic membrane that usually follows a long-standing middle ear infection emanating from acute otitis media (AOM), otitis media with effusion (OME), or persistent negative pressure of the middle ear for an extended period of time (1,2). Its chronicity is declared when it persists for more than 3 months from the date of onset (if known) or from the date of diagnosis (if onset is unknown) (3).

COM can be classified as chronic suppurative otitis media when there is an active aural discharge and as a chronic non-suppurative otitis media when there it is dry. Further, this

disease entity is subdivided into mucosal and squamous based on the histologic features of the middle ear mucosa and the edges of the perforated tympanic membrane (TM) (1,2).

In general, COM is common world over, being more common in developing nations than in developed countries as a result of a variety of factors including socioeconomic ones pathogen exposure, respiratory infection, and nasal obstruction and health care infrastructure (1,4). In the former groups, the prevalence of CSOM was quite different by region and country, from extending from 0.3 to 14% (5). Beyond this, it has been also described as a Neglected Tropical Disease (6).

COM is estimated to have an incidence rate of 31 million episodes per year, or 4.8 new episodes per 1,000 people (all ages). It evenly affects children of both sexes and all age groups, with 22% of all cases affecting children <5 years of age. The prevalence of COM varies widely among countries, but it disproportionately affects people in low-income and middle-income countries, resource limited areas, certain indigenous groups and people with certain underlying conditions such as cleft palate and Down Syndrome (5,6). COM is the most common ear-related problem in developing countries (9).

In poorly managed conditions, COM can cause extracranial and intracranial complications in as much as 80% of the patients, including subperiosteal abscesses and brain abscesses (10). Likewise, chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is a major cause of acquired hearing impairment in pediatric population, especially in developing countries (11). The prevalence of CSOM appears to be comparable between males and females. Exact prevalence in different age subsets is not clearly established; however, some studies estimate the yearly incidence of CSOM to be 39 cases per 100,000 in children younger than 16 years (12).

The risk factors for the development of COM have not been exhaustively established in the available literature, and well-designed rigorous studies that analyze pre-existing conditions with the incidence of COM from Ethiopian perspective are lacking, particularly in resource-poor settings (11). Hence, the present study is designed with the purpose of assessing the magnitude of chronic otitis media and its associated factors in pediatric population in resource-scarce countries by taking the case of otolaryngology clinics at tertiary centers in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Notably, COM has potentially deleterious complications if inadequately managed, especially in the resource-poor countries such as Ethiopia, owing to complex reasons including poverty, ignorance, dearth of specialists and limited access to medical care that worsen the course of the disease (1). World widely, each year approximately 21 thousand people, equating 33 per 10 million people, die due to the complications of otitis media. Mortality is higher in the first year of life (85.4 per 10 million) and in the age group 1–4 years of age (90.5). Particularly, the Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has disproportionately high rates, with slight variation from East (73.49), Central (96.2) to West (91.8) (13), and the prevalence of CSOM in SSA ranges from 0.4% to 4.2% (11). Moreover, besides of its clinical complications such as hearing disability, CSOM continued to pose serious socioeconomic burden as its estimated cost of treatment is higher than the monthly minimum wage for individuals in Nigerian population (14).

In Ethiopian context, despite the fact that there is scarcity of data regarding the exact magnitude and impact of COM, COM and its subsequent complications are usually neglected conditions due to insufficient funds, work force, facilities, and knowledge. Thus, the behavioral aspect of stakeholders has received only little attention although it has been shown to result in profound negative impact. Hence, there is a need to conduct such studies to explore the existing pattern of COM in this regard, with a focus on maternal and child-related characteristics that would contribute to CSOM.

1.3 Significance of the study

The findings of this study will be an input to the country's health sector transformation plan, which aims to improve equity, coverage and utilization of essential health services. Moreover, this study is expected to contribute to the existing body of knowledge regarding magnitude of chronic otitis media and its associated factors in children attending otolaryngology clinics at the study setting, thereby shedding some light to the potential areas for evidence-based preventive interventions. Furthermore, the findings are expected to be of particular importance to local planners and health-policy makers to design policies that would

alleviate the burden of this neglected tropical disease among vulnerable age groups. Finally, this study will also serve as an additional information to other interested investigators in similar research projects.

2. Literature review

2.1 Overview of chronic otitis media

CSOM is usually defined as ear disease which is typically characterized by an aural discharge through a perforated tympanic membrane for more than 2 to 6 weeks. However, if the duration of the discharge is not exactly known, perforations that are large (covering >2% of the tympanic membrane) are more likely to be associated with CSOM (13,14). Chronic suppuration can occur on the background of cholesteatoma or not, and the clinical history of both conditions can be very alike. It is the most severe form of OM and it is the type of OM most likely to persist without treatment (17). CSOM is usually classified into two main groups: tubotympanic (TT) and atticoantral (AA) disease. Tubotympanic disease is characterized by a perforation of the pars tensa. Atticoantral disease most commonly involves the pars flaccida and is characterized by the formation of a retraction pocket in which keratin accumulates to produce cholesteatoma (18).

In contrast to that of developed countries, where CSOM is now very uncommon, in developing countries, CSOM occurs as a complication of AOM with perforation and can be a major health issue. Children with immunodeficiency and some indigenous populations are also at significantly increased risk. For instance, in rural and remote communities in northern Australia, more than 20% of young children are affected (13,14).

2.2 Magnitude of COM

Global estimated CSOM incidence rate is 4.76 per thousand people for a total of 31 million cases, with 22.6% of these cases occurring annually in children younger of five years. Latin America Andean is the area with the lowest incidence (1.70 per thousand), followed by Asia Pacific High Income (3.02) and North America High Income (3.06). Oceania has the highest

incidence with 9.37, while two other areas have an incidence higher than 7: Sub-Saharan Africa Central (7.56) and West (7.22) (13).

Globally, CSOM incidence rate is highest in the first year of life (15.40 per thousand) and reaches its lowest value after 65 years of age (2.51). In the first year of life, Asia Pacific High Income has the lowest incidence rate (1.59 per thousand), while Oceania has the highest (35.96). The proportion of cases occurring in U5 vary from 1.8% in the Asia Pacific High Income, to 38.9% in Oceania and 41.0% in Sub-Saharan Africa Central (13). Gautam and colleagues tried to study the clinical and epidemiological profile of suppurative otitis media following surgery at an Indian tertiary care center by analyzing 265 patients aging from 11 to 20 years. In the study, 72.82% patients belonged to lower socioeconomic status. Tubotympanic type constituted majority 207 (78.12%) cases followed by atticofacial type in 58 (21.88%) cases (19).

Similarly, in a cross-sectional study conducted among children aging 5 to 15 years at monastic schools in different parts of Nepal over a three-year period from 2017 to 2019, chronic otitis media was the most common otoscopic finding during the screening, affecting a total of 344 (10.83%) children (20). The study also added that, out of these affected children, hearing loss of varying degrees was observed in half (n=172) of the children, indicating that COM is the main cause of avoidable hearing loss (20).

Several prevalence studies of CSOM have been conducted across different regions. In Britain, 0.9% of children and 0.5% of adults were affected by CSOM. In Israel, only 0.039% of children are estimated to have CSOM (16). In South Korean population older than 4 years of age, authors obtained the prevalence of 3.13% for CSOM (21) in their cross-sectional analysis of a nationwide health survey, while the prevalence of obvious cholesteatoma was 0.34% and the weighted prevalence of COM was 3.8% (19). Moreover, a cross-sectional community-based survey was conducted to determine the prevalence of CSOM and associated disabling hearing impairment among school children aged six to 16 years in Socotra Island, Yemen, from 20 April 2011 to 20 June 2011. And the prevalence of CSOM was 7.4% (23). Similarly, high prevalence of otological diseases in school going

children of Kathmandu valley, with CSOM affecting 5.7% of the children and 85.9% were tubotympanic type (24).

A cross-sectional study was carried out among 810 children aged 6–59 months in Gasabo district of Kigali city, Rwanda to determine the prevalence and care seeking behavior for middle ear infections in children. The authors documented that the prevalence of middle ear infections was 5.8%, of whom 4% had chronic suppurative otitis media (25). Similarly, a community-based cross-sectional study was undertaken among children aged 4 to 6 years in Chikhwawa District, Southern Malawi, utilising a village-level cluster design. The prevalence estimates of CSOM, unilateral hearing impairment and bilateral hearing impairment were 5.4%, 24.5%, and 12.5%, respectively (26).

Moreover, in Tanzanian population, in 2019, Abraham and others assessed a total of 5591 patients to determine the prevalence and etiological agents for chronic suppurative otitis media. In their study, they demonstrated that only 79 (1.4%) had chronic suppurative otitis media. Of note, the study stated that children younger than 5 years accounted to the highest proportion (26.6%) of all cases of chronic suppurative otitis media (27).

2.3 Factors affecting CSOM

The prevalence of CSOM is related with various host and environmental factors including crowded habitation, access to medical care including vaccinations, antibiotics use, exposure to smoking, bottle feeding, and poor nutrition/hygiene (5). The above-mentioned South Korean study showed that the prevalence of CSOM increased with age and had a female predominance (21). Further, the study revealed that age >19 years, hearing threshold, the presence of tinnitus, diabetes, drinking alcohol, residence in a row house, and education level of the mother were significantly associated with CSOM (21).

In a case–control study conducted in Auckland, New Zealand from May 2011 until November 2013, it was shown that children with COM with effusion frequently had nasal obstruction, always snored or often snored, spent more hours per week in daycare, had frequent colds, had siblings who had undergone tympanostomy tube placement, underwent long labour, and had early introduction of cow's milk (4). In the previous South Korean

analysis, factors that showed high odds ratios (ORs) for COM were pulmonary tuberculosis, chronic rhinosinusitis, mild hearing impairment, moderate hearing impairment, tinnitus, increased hearing thresholds in pure tone audiometry in the right ear, and left ear (22).

The aforementioned Yemeni study identified that history of ear discharge in the last 12 months, swimming in local pools, recurrent respiratory tract infection more than three times per year, and overcrowding with more than three families per house were the significant independent contributing factors to CSOM in the studied population (23). The previous Rwandan study reported that children who live in an urban setting were less likely to develop middle ear infections but they were more likely to develop middle ear infections if exposed to household smoke. The authors also added that parents were unlikely to know that their child had an ear infection (25). In the previous Malawian report, a trend towards increased risk of CSOM was observed with sleeping in a house with >2 other children (26). In Tanzanian setting, a male preponderance 43 (54.4%) was noted and the left ear (58.2%) was more commonly affected compared to the right ear (27).

In the setting of South African authors, Hallbauer reported that a high percentage of children (54.2%) with CSOM have associated pathology such as HIV infection (28). Likewise, a systematic review by Choffor-Nchinda demonstrated that cleft palate and immunosuppressive ailments are important contributors of otitis media with effusion (OME) in Africa children and adults (29).

In conclusion, the reviewed literature reveals that the definition of COM and CSOM are controversial and that the magnitude of CSOM in developing countries is disproportionately higher as a result of different factors. Moreover, it was noted that there is scarcity of context-specific data regarding the magnitude of chronic suppurative otitis media and its associated factors among COM children attending otolaryngology clinics at tertiary centers in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, validating the current study that aimed to narrow this knowledge gap.

2.4 Conceptual framework

This is a conceptual framework developed specifically for this study by the principal investigator after reviewing related literatures (22,30) in which this study is aimed to focus. The framework tries to figure out associated factors that affect the development of CSOM among the pediatric population, and believed to support the study entitled “*Magnitude of chronic suppurative otitis media and its associated factors among children with COM attending Ear, Nose and Throat clinic at tertiary centers in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia*”.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for factors affecting development of chronic suppurative otitis media among children attending Ear, Nose and Throat clinic at tertiary centers

3. Objective of study

3.1 General objective

- To assess the magnitude of chronic suppurative otitis media and its associated factors in children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

3.2 Specific objectives

- To find out the magnitude of chronic suppurative otitis media in children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers from October 1st to December 31st, 2021
- To identify the factors associated with chronic suppurative otitis media in children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers from October 1st to December 31st, 2021

4. Methods and Materials

4.1 Study area and period

The study was conducted at three selected government hospitals in Addis Ababa. Addis Ababa is the capital city of Ethiopia, which is in the center of the nation in the foothills of mount Entoto about 2500 meters above sea level. The city has a population of about 5,006,000 inhabitants and fourteen government hospitals. Addis Ababa is the political capital of Africa, and where the African Union is headquartered. It is also the location for the United Nations Economic Commission of Africa.

One of the hospitals at which the study was conducted is Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital (TASH), Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. TASH is the largest and oldest public hospital of the country providing high level of clinical care for millions of people and training to health science students from different parts of the country and the Horn of Africa as well. This teaching hospital has several specialty and sub-speciality clinics delivering specialized care to over half a million patients annually and about 1500 outpatients daily. This 850-bedded

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hospital embodies 1121 physicians (faculties and postgraduate trainees), 379 nurses, 115 other health professionals along with 950 permanent and contract administrative staff dedicated to providing a range of health care services including otorhinolaryngology care.

St. Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College (SPHMMC) was founded in July 1947 during the reign of Emperor Haile Selassie, and it is the second largest hospital in Ethiopia. The hospital has more than 2500 clinical, academic and administrative staff. While the inpatient capacity is more than 700 beds, the college sees more than 2000 emergency and outpatient clients daily.

Yekatit XII Hospital Medical is established in 1923 as one of modern medical service delivery center. Currently, it has more than 335 beds serving the community within the catchment area, more than 25% for maternity program. The clinic is run once a week by a team of seniors, residents, nursing and other staff. The hospitals were selected for presence of organized ENT clinics providing services for both pediatric and adult age groups. Data were collected from October 1st to December 31st, 2021.

4.2 Study design

An institution-based, cross-sectional study design was employed.

4.4 Source population

Children with COM visiting Ear, Nose and Throat clinics of public hospitals of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

4.5 Study population

Children with COM visiting Ear, Nose and Throat clinics of public hospitals of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia from October 1st to December 31st, 2021 GC and who fulfill the inclusion criteria

4.6 Eligibility criteria

4.6.1 Inclusion criteria

- Children with confirmed diagnosis of COM

- Children younger than 5 years of age by the time of data collection

4.6.2 Exclusion criteria

- Children coming from daycare centers whose mothers are deceased before the data collection period
- Children with unsettled diagnosis of ear disease
- Children whose accompanying caregivers are seriously ill during the time of data collection

4.7 Sample size determination

The sample size for this study is calculated using a single population proportion formula. Taking the proportion of children having CSOM to be 13.2% from previous conducted in Nepal (31).

$$n^0 = \frac{z^2 p(1-p)}{e^2}$$

n = the required sample size

p = the proportion of children having CSOM-13.2%

$Z_{\alpha/2}$ = the critical value at 95% confidence level = 1.96

e = precision (margin of error) = 5%

N = the total number of COM patients attending ENT clinics during the study period=390

Accordingly,

$$n^0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 * 0.132(1 - 0.132)}{0.05^2}$$

$$n^0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 * 0.132(0.868)}{0.05^2}$$

$$n^0 = 176$$

Hence, to compute the final sample size using the correction formula as the total source population from the hospital is less than 10,000 (N=390)

$$n = \frac{n^0}{1 + (n^0 - 1)/N}$$

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$$n = \frac{176}{1+(176-1)/390} = 121$$

Therefore, adding 10% for contingency, the final sample size for this study became 133.

4.8 Sampling procedures

The study participants were selected from each unit of the hospital by proportion to population size allocation, based on the total numbers of COM patients in each ENT unit using proportional stratified random sampling method from those who fulfill the eligibility criteria.

To determine the proportional sample=>

The average number of COM seen at each ENT center *Total sample size (133) divided by total source population, as calculated below:

$$\text{TASH: } \frac{131 \cdot 140}{390} \approx 47 \text{ patients}$$

$$\text{SPHMMC: } \frac{131 \cdot 130}{390} \approx 44 \text{ patients}$$

$$\text{YHMC: } \frac{131 \cdot 120}{390} \approx 40 \text{ patients}$$

Then after, at each unit, patients were recruited randomly using simple random sampling technique.

4.9 Data collection tools and procedures

Data were collected from eligible caregivers using interviewer-administered, structured, pre-tested data collection tool, and patients' medical records were retrieved and reviewed whenever need arises. The data collection format includes questions divided into three parts (background information, clinical variables, and outcome parameters) and it was adapted from related literatures (30). Data were gathered from logbook records of ENT patient registry over three months (from October 1st, 2021 to December 31st, 2021). Two professional healthcare workers were recruited and trained on data collection procedure

4.10 Study variables

4.10.1 Dependent variable

- Chronic suppurative otitis media

4.10.2 Independent variables

- Age of the child
- Age of the caregiver
- Sex
- Residence
- Marital status of the caregiver
- Educational level of the caregiver
- Caregiver's occupational status
- Average household monthly income in ETB
- Family size
- Birth order of the child
- Anthropometric parameters of the child
- History of allergy/atopy
- History of upper respiratory tract infections
- History of chronic nasal obstruction
- History of snoring
- History of attending day-care centers
- Family history of otitis media
- Patient history of acute or recurrent otitis media
- History of in-door tobacco smoke exposure
- Maternal history of tobacco smoking during pregnancy
- History of breast feeding
- Exclusively breast fed for at least 5 months
- History of aural trauma
- Any history of chronic medical condition
- Vaccination history
- History of measles attack
- Preauricular sinus present
- History of instillation of oil/other homemade liquids in ears

4.11 Operational definition

- **Recurrent AOM:** The occurrence of 3 or more episodes in 6 months or 4 episodes within 12 months

- **CSOM:** refers to ear discharge through a perforated tympanic membrane for more than 2 to 6 weeks

4.12 Data processing and analysis

Data entering, coding, and cleaning were performed using Epi-info version 7.0 and then exported to SPSS version 26 to carry out statistical analysis. Frequency and cross tabulation were used to check for missed value and variables. The demographic and clinical characteristics of patients were computed by using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, percentage, frequencies, interquartile range and standard deviation. Logistic regression was used to determine associations between the independent and dependent variables. Those variables with p value of ≤ 2.5 in bivariable logistic regression were included in the multivariable logistic regression model to compute adjusted odds ratio at 95% confidence interval. Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test was run to ascertain the fitness of the model, where p value of >0.05 indicates data fitness. Variables with p-value ≤ 0.05 were considered as statistically associated with the outcome variable. Finally, the study findings were presented using diagrams, tables and figures.

4.13 Data quality management

To guarantee the data quality, data collection tool was prepared after thorough review of relevant literatures and related studies. The tool was pretested before the data collection process in 10% of the total sample size among COM attending Ras Desta Damtew Hospital. An English version, pretested questionnaire was used to collect data. Brief training for the data collectors (two health professionals) about the process of data collection was given before the process of data collection. The data collection procedure was closely supervised, and each day, filled questionnaires were double-checked manually for consistency and completeness by data collectors and principal investigator before proceeding to analysis.

4.14 Ethical consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from Ethical Review Committee of GAMBY Medical and Business College. Clearance letter was submitted to the medical directors and Research

Directorate of each hospital being carrying out the actual data collection for the study. This was followed by introduction & familiarization of the data collectors with the study subunits. Before interviewing clients, the purpose of the study was briefly explained and written informed consent was sought. During data collection, study participants were informed that the information collected will be kept anonymous and confidential.

4.15 Dissemination of the study findings

The findings of this study will be submitted to the Department of Public Health of GAMBY Medical and Business College as a partial fulfillment of a master's degree in General Public Health. The outcome of this study will be presented to the higher officials of the college. Additionally, as the results are expected to contribute for the local health policy makers, effort will be exerted to notify Addis Ababa Health Bureau on the overall findings of the study. Finally, the manuscript will be submitted to a peer-reviewed scientific journal for possible publication.

5. Results

5.1. Socio-demographic characteristics

This study included data derived from a hundred and twenty chronic otitis media patients who attending three tertiary public hospital of Addis Ababa, after excluding thirteen patients who didn't fulfill the inclusion criteria. Among the studied children, about two-third (78; 65%) were males and the remaining 42 (35%) were females. Children's age ranged from seven months to five years, with median (interquartile range) of 3 (2–4) years. The corresponding mean (\pm standard deviation) age of children's mothers was 36.62 (\pm 4.65) years, with the range extending from 20 to 44 years (Table 1).

Regarding current residence, majority (66;55%) were dwellers of Addis Ababa whereas the rest 54 (45%) claim to reside out of the capital. Most of the interviewed caregivers (84;70%) were married by the time of data collection while nineteen (15.8%) were divorced. The highest educational status attained by the caregivers was primary education as it was reported by 66 (55%) of them while about a quarter (28;23.3%) stated to be illiterate. In relation to

occupational category, close to half (58;48.3%) reported to be unemployed while about a third (38;3.7%) were employed. Besides, nearly half (55;45.8%) of the caregivers stated to have a family income not more than 7000 ETB a month, as detailed in Table 1.

Apart from this, the family size was three in thirty-six (30%) of children, and about half (52;43.3%) of the children were the first siblings in the birth order of their respective families. Moreover, while most (104;86.7%) of the children were breastfed during their infancy, only seventy-three (70.2%) were exclusively breastfed in the first five months of their lives (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution by socio-demographic of children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers from October 1st to December 31st, 2021

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Child's age		
< 2 years	21	17.5
≥ years	99	82.5
Maternal age		
≤ 24 years	8	6.7
25–34 years	81	67.5
≥35 years	31	25.8
Child's sex		
Male	81	67.5
Female	39	32.5
Residence		
Urban	68	56.7
Rural	52	43.3
Caregiver's marital status		
Unmarried	14	11.7
Married	84	70.0
Divorced	19	15.8
Widowed	3	2.5
Maternal educational status		
Illiterate	28	23.3
Primary education	66	55
Secondary education	20	16.7
College diploma +	6	5.0
Maternal occupational category		
Unemployed	58	48.3

Self-employed	38	31.7
Employed	24	20.0
Monthly household income		
≤5100 ETB	24	20.0
5101 to 7000 ETB	31	25.8
7001 to 8000 ETB	23	19.2
8000 to 9160 ETB	18	15.0
>9160 ETB	24	20.0
Family size		
2	16	13.3
3	36	30.0
4	31	25.8
5	22	18.31
≥6	15	12.5
Birth order		
First	52	43.3
Second	30	25.0
Third	22	18.3
≥Fourth	16	13.3
Breast feeding		
No	16	13.3
Yes	104	86.7
Exclusive breast feeding (n=104)		
No	31	29.8
Yes	73	70.2

ETB: Ethiopian Birr

5.2 Clinical characteristics

With regard to mid upper arm circumference of the studied children, three-fourths (89;74.2%) measured between 11.5 to 12.4 cm. Almost one-third (38;31.7%) of the children were described to have previous attack of measles whereas majority (94;78.3%) were fully vaccinated as per the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) schedule. Forty-eight children had history of allergy (40%) while a hundred (83.3%) had history of previous upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) (Table 2).

Further, only a third (40;33.3%) of all children had nasal obstruction as per parental reporting, half (59;49.2%) had snoring episodes during sleeping. Well more than a third (45;37.5%) of the children had attended a public daycare center. Two-fifths (48;40%) had positive family history of otitis media while majority (86;71.7%) had recurrent attacks of

acute otitis media. Nearly a quarter (28;23.3%) of all had history of exposure to indoor smoke and seven (5.8%) had been exposed to tobacco smoke during the prenatal period (Table 2). Forty-two (35%) had a pre-existing chronic medical condition diagnosed by a health care profession. Of these, HIV/AIDS, diabetes mellitus, cleft palate and Down’s syndrome were the common comorbidities as they appeared in 15 (35.7%), 10 (23.8%), 9 (21.4%) and (8 (19%) of the patients, respectively. Only ten (8.3%) preauricular sinus (pits) upon clinical inspection while fifty-six (46.7%) had history of instillation of oil/other homemade liquids in ears in the affected ear. Finally, only twenty (16.7%) had history of trauma involving the affected ear (Table 2).

Table 2. Clinical characteristics of children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers from October 1st to December 31st, 2021

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
MUAC		
< 11.5 cm	16	13.3
11.5 to 12.4 cm	89	74.2
12.5 to 13.4 cm	13	10.8
≥13.5 cm	2	1.7
Measles history		
No	82	68.3
Yes	38	31.7
Vaccinated to age		
No	26	21.7
Yes	94	78.3
Allergy		
No	72	60
Yes	48	40
URTI		
No	20	16.7
Yes	100	83.3
Nasal obstruction		
No	80	66.7
Yes	40	33.3
Snoring		
No	61	50.8
Yes	59	49.2
Day care		
No	75	62.5
Yes	45	37.5
Family history		

No	72	60.0
Yes	48	40.0
Recurrent OM		
No	34	28.3
Yes	86	71.7
Indoor smoking		
No	92	76.7
Yes	28	23.3
Intra-pregnancy smoking		
No	113	94.2
Yes	7	5.8
Comorbidity		
No	78	65
Yes	42	35
Preauricular sinus		
No	110	91.7
Yes	10	8.3
Instillation		
No	64	53.3
Yes	56	46.7
Ear trauma		
No	100	83.3
Yes	20	16.7

MUAC: Mid upper arm circumference; URTI: Upper respiratory tract infection; OM: Otitis media

5.3 Magnitude of chronic suppurative otitis media

Of the total participants, 34.2% (95% CI: 26–43) of the studied children were diagnosed of CSOM while the remaining two-thirds were recorded to have chronic otitis media with effusion, as depicted in Figure 2. Moreover, a quarter (28;23.3%) of the disease were bilateral while the remaining majority (92;76.7%) were unilateral.

Figure 2. Types of chronic otitis media among children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers from October 1st to December 31st, 2021

5.4 Factors affecting CSOM

In this study, twenty-eight variables, namely child's age, maternal age, child's sex, residence, caregivers' marital status, maternal educational status, maternal occupational category, monthly household income, family size, birth order, history of breast feeding, exclusive breast feeding, MUAC, measles history, vaccinated to age, allergy, URTI, nasal obstruction, snoring, day care, family history, history of recurrent OM, indoor smoking, intra-pregnancy smoking, comorbidity, sinus, instillation, and ear trauma were considered in the regression analysis. In order to determine the factors associated with CSOM while controlling possible confounders, independent variables that yielded p value of ≤ 0.25 in binary logistic regression were exported to multiple regression model to compute adjusted odds ratio in determining CSOM.

Accordingly, eleven factors, namely monthly household income, history of breast feeding, exclusive breast feeding, vaccinated to age, history of attending a daycare center, allergy, URTI, presence of comorbidity, recurrent AOM, prenatal smoking, and laterality were observed in bivariable analysis to be associated with development of CSOM among the

studied children. Following multivariable logistic analysis, the only variables that showed statistically significant association with CSOM were exclusive breast feeding, vaccination to age, attendance to day care centers, presence of comorbidity, and recurrent AOM.

Specifically, this study showed that when compared to those who had been exclusively breast fed, children who were not on exclusive breastfeeding for the at least the first five months of their lives were more likely to have CSOM [AOR=14.00(95%CI: 4.42,44.36)]. Similarly, children who were not fully vaccinated according the EPI schedule had significantly higher likelihood of having CSOM [AOR=10.44 (95%CI: (2.91,37.48)] in comparison to their counterparts who had been vaccinated as per the EPI schedule (Table 3).

On the other hand, when compared to children who did not attend a daycare center, children who attended a public daycare center previously showed higher odds of having CSOM [AOR=3.46 (95%CI: (1.12,10.63)]. Moreover, patients with a certain comorbidity were more likely to have CSOM [AOR=3.85 (95%CI: (1.28,11.56)] in reference to children who had never been diagnosed of a chronic medical condition. Finally, compared to children with no recurrent attacks of AOM, children who had recurrent history of AOM showed higher odds of having CSOM, with AOR of 6.74 (95%CI: 1.65,27.58), according to the multiple regression analysis (Table 3).

Table 3. Factors associated with CSOM among children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics at tertiary centers from October 1st to December 31st, 2021

Variable	CSOM		COR(95% CI)	AOR(95% CI)
	No (%)	Yes (%)		
Monthly household income				
≤5100 ETB	10	14	2.23(0.73,7.43)	-
5101 to 7000 ETB	21	10	0.79(0.26,2.43)	-
7001 to 8000 ETB	19	4	0.35(0.09,1.36)	-
8000 to 9160 ETB	14	4	0.48(0.12,1.90)	-
>9160 ETB	15	9	1	-
Breast feeding				
No	8	8	2.15(0.74,6.23)	-
Yes	71	33	1	-
Exclusive breast feeding				
No	18	29	8.19(3.49,19.23)	14.00(4.42,44.36)***
Yes	61	12	1	1
Vaccinated to age				

No	9	17	5.51(2.17,13.98)	10.44(2.91,37.48)***
Yes	70	24	1	1
Day care				
No	55	20	1	1
Yes	24	21	2.41(1.11,5.24)	3.46(1.12,10.63)*
Allergy				
No	53	19	1	
Yes	26	22	2.36(1.09,5.11)	-
URTI				
No	16	4	1	-
Yes	63	37	2.35(0.73,7.56)	-
Presence of comorbidity				
No	58	20	1	1
Yes	21	21	2.90(1.32,6.39)	3.85(1.28,11.56)*
Recurrent AOM				
No	35	6	1	1
Yes	44	35	4.64(1.75,12.28)	6.74(1.65,27.58)**
Prenatal smoking				
No	76	37	2.74(0.58,12.87)	-
Yes	3	4	1	-
Laterality				
Left	22	19	2.59(0.90,7.42)	-
Right	36	15	1.25(0.44,3.56)	-
Both	21	7	1	-

Only variables with p value <0.25 in bivariable logistic regression are shown here

*P value < 0.05; **P value < 0.01; *** P value < 0.001

6. Discussion

The present study aimed to the magnitude of chronic suppurative otitis media and its associated factors by analyzing clinic-demographic characteristics of children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Subsequently, the study discovered several important findings. The present study showed that a significant portion of children with COM have suppuration, affecting more than one-third of them. Moreover, it was revealed that PAFP uptake was contributed by factors such as lack of exclusive breastfeeding history, lack of full vaccination to age, history of attending a daycare center, presence of comorbidity, and recurrent AOM.

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Specifically, this study demonstrated that one-third of children with COM have suppuration. This is in agreement with the Nigerian report that stated that CSOM account for 31.1% of all otologic presentations (14). It was also close to the pattern noted in Tanzanian children younger than 5 years wherein these subsets of the population accounted to the highest proportion (26.6%) of all cases of chronic suppurative otitis media (27). This figure is shocking given the fact that the disease is potentially preventable. Also, this finding classifies the region in the highest category for CSOM according to WHO stratification which categorizes countries with >4% prevalence into the highest category (11). Moreover, this figure was quite higher than the finding reported in southern Malawi and Nepalese populations in which the prevalence estimate of CSOM were standing at 5.4% (26) and 5.7% (24), respectively. Similarly, it was higher than the burden noted in Yemeni setting, where the prevalence of CSOM among children was 7.4% (23). The high proportion of disease in this segment of the population can be partly justified by their relative immature immunity, making them prone to infection and their relatively short and horizontal Eustachian tube, exposing them to recurrent ear infections (27).

The large difference in the magnitude of CSOM between this study and the previous estimate in other settings could be attributed to the relative abundance of poverty-related factors and poor access to health care among children in resource-challenged regions such as ours. Moreover, the inter-regional variation can be explained by differences length of follow-up, sample size, the characteristics of the studied population, methodological design, and differences microbiological profile. For instance, the Yemeni study was community-based and included school children aging six to sixteen years using while the current study was facility-based and limited to preschool children not older than five.

Lack of exclusive breast feeding in the first five months of life was related to CSOM in this study, and it is in line with several studies that showed that exclusive breast feeding has a protective effect against a variety of middle ear infections during early childhood (4,32). The present study demonstrated that properly vaccinated children have lower risk of contracting CSOM, and this confirms the report that vaccines provide protective benefit against OM (32).

Besides, immunization with pneumococcal conjugate vaccine has been proven to reduce invasive pneumococcal disease (33).

Further, the current study highlighted that children with a coexisting medical condition such as HIV/AIDS and diabetes mellitus have higher risk of developing CSOM. This is supported by the work of South African authors, who reported that a high percentage of children with CSOM have associated pathology (28). Likewise, a systematic review by Choffor-Nchinda demonstrated that cleft palate and immunosuppressive ailments are important contributors of otitis media (29).

In this particular study, independent association was found between history of recurrent acute otitis media attack and CSOM. The possible explanation for this finding can be multiple, and it includes the possibility of underdiagnosis by lower level healthcare professionals and the impression that patients might be subjected to improper treatment including traditional remedies, which can be erosive to the middle ear structures. Finally, in keeping with reports elsewhere (34), having a positive history of attending a public daycare center was associated with development of CSOM. This can be due to overcrowding which in turn predisposes children to a range of otopathogenic microbes.

7. Strengths and Limitations

7.1 Strength

- The current study was done at three otorhinolaryngology center, making it generalizable to other similar populations attending public health facilities.
- A comprehensive set of variables were included and the sample size was relatively large, allowing us to have confidence in external validity of the current findings.

7.2 Limitations

- This study is expected to be prone for the limitation of a cross-sectional study design, and as a consequence, establishing causal relationship would be impossible.
- Recall bias can be a concern in interpreting the findings as participants were meant to respond some variables by recalling past events such history of smoking during

pregnancy and history of breast feeding, among others.8. Conclusion and recommendations

8.1 Conclusion

The magnitude of chronic suppurative otitis media among children with COM attending otorhinolaryngology clinics in tertiary centers of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia is high, affecting one in three preschool children. Not being exclusive breast fed, being not fully vaccinated to age, history of attending daycare center, presence of comorbidity, and recurrent AOM were the factor that contributed to suppuration among the preschool children.

8.2 Recommendation

Based on the findings obtained in the study, the following recommendations can be forwarded.

To health professionals,

Whenever possible, trained health professionals should be psychoeducate caregivers about the mechanisms to reduce the incidence of such ear problems. Health education through health extension workers to prevent ear diseases, which is one of the major causes of deafness, is necessary to reduce the burden of chronic suppurative otitis media and prevent the vulnerable children from subsequent disability. with emphasis to those with predisposing factors such as lack of exclusive breastfeeding history, lack of full vaccination to age, history of attending daycare center, presence of comorbidity, and recurrent AOM.

To local health policy makers,

Local policy makers, along with concerned stakeholders, should consider awareness creation modalities via as mass media and health extension workforce to consolidate the caregivers' knowledge on the care of affected children on top of the need for early screening and diagnosis of such vulnerable population.

To researchers,

Future studies should be done to validate the current findings, and they should employ stronger study designs including microbiological and oto-microscopic data to have an in-depth evidence.

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